

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPECIAL COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: One of the primary tasks of education is to establish national and universal values in the consciousness of the learner, to prepare the ground for the active participation of young students in socio-economic relations with the formation of practical life skills in order to find their rightful place in the society in the future. From this point of view, one of the main tasks of the educational process is not only to provide students with knowledge in subjects, but also to apply the acquired knowledge and skills, and to direct them to the formation of skills to use them in everyday life.

Key words: educational system, concepts, pedagogic scientists, special competences, professional competence, interpretations and definitions.

Today, the educational system is faced with problems such as the concept of competence, its content, boundaries, and the structure of its components, which are interpreted differently by researchers.

Concepts of "competence" and "competence" are widely used in the psychological-pedagogical literature and in the scientific works of many pedagogic scientists from our country and abroad . The competent approach to the education system began to be formed in foreign literature in the 60s of the last century, and the issue of "Competence" has been studied by scientists for many years. They are N.A. Muslimov, Sh.Sh. Sharipov, H.F. Rashidov, S.Yu. Makhmudov, O.A. Koysynov, M.Kh. Saidov, R. White, Dj. Raven, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, V.I. Baidenko, A.V. Khutorsky, S.I. Ojegov and others. E.F.Zeer, I.A.Zimnyaya, V.I.Baydenko, A.A.Verbitsky and others conducted scientific research and research on issues of competence formation. Special competences reflect the specific characteristics of the field outside of a specific subject or subject of professional activity. Special competences can be considered as the implementation of general and basic competences in the subject of study, a certain direction of professional activity .

Of course, all three types of competencies are interconnected and develop simultaneously. It forms an individual style of pedagogical activity, creates a holistic image of a specialist and ultimately ensures the formation of his professional competence. M.D. Ilyazova divides competencies into general and special competencies.

Competencies in professional education are divided into basic (basic skills) and special (professional skills) competencies. Basic competencies are necessary for any specialist and include general professional and social-psychological competencies, and special competencies include professional skills and special social competencies specific to this or that specialist. V.G. Pishchulin "professional competence, be it general or special, in most cases memory, logical and creative thinking, reflection, agility, dexterity, perseverance, determination, orderly and keeping one's word, not giving in to passions, observation, curiosity, attentiveness , leads to the appearance of qualities such as seriousness and the ability to engage in dealings", he writes A.V. Khutorskoy divides competencies as follows:

1) basic (basic) competencies, which have the characteristics of multifunctionality, extreme subjectivity and multidimensionality.

2) core professional competence includes crosscultural and cross-sectoral knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for adaptation and effective functioning of this specialist.

3) special competences are designed to help in the implementation of a certain type of professional activity. Core competencies play an important role in this. V.I. Baydenko described the concept of "professional competence" as follows:

- to have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities necessary to work in one's specialty, to have the characteristics of autonomy and flexibility at the same time in partially solving professional problems;

- development of cooperation with colleagues in a professional interpersonal environment;

- the design structure of the standards, including the performance criterion (quality measure), the field of application, and the required knowledge;

- effective use of abilities that allow effective implementation of professional activities

according to the requirements of the employer ;

- an integrated combination of knowledge , characteristics and skills that allow a person to successfully perform work in the modern work environment .

In his research, N.A. Muslimov emphasized the basis of the formation of the teacher's professional competence in the form of 6 qualities, these are:

1) Motivational qualities (covers the needs, motives and goals of a person for his chosen profession, which are formed and developed throughout his life);

2) Intellectual potential (on the basis of all official documents, the teacher strives to transfer information and data, to form knowledge, skills and qualifications);

3) Volitional qualities (striving for the goal, overcoming internal and external obstacles, physical and mental stress, self-control and initiative qualities);

4) Practical skills (psychological, pedagogical, methodical and technical-technological skills, actions, individual skills in various spheres of activity and communication);

5) Emotional qualities (the formation of the necessary skills to manage one's emotions (anger, anger, anxiety, resentment, jealousy, sympathy, shame, pride, fear, joy, love, etc.) and to understand one's emotional states and their causes);

6) Self-control (freedom in choosing goals and means of achieving them, conscientiousness, critical approach to one's activities, comprehensiveness and understanding of actions, comparing one's own behavior with that of others, confidence in the future, maintaining and managing one's physical and psychological condition at the desired level get).

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Psychologist A.K. Makarova says that the concept of professional competence of a future teacher includes all his qualities, with the help of which a person can achieve high results during his teaching career. In his opinion, professional competence is such labor activity of a technology teacher, as a result of which a high level of professional activity is carried out and the future teacher shows himself as a person. Thus, A.K. Makarova further expands the content of the concept of professional competence of the teacher, including the subjective characteristics of the specialist (Psikhologiya professionalizma M.1996). N.V. Kuzmina describes the special competence of a technological education teacher in the design of technological processes as follows: The professional competence of a technological education teacher, that is, the competence related to the design of technological processes, should consist of 5 special competencies.

These are:

1. Design competence - the teaching subject, that is, the design of technological processes in the science of technology.

2. Methodological competence - the ability to apply the method of formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications for the design of technological processes.

3. Socio-psychological competence - taking into account the student's age characteristics (in the process of treatment) in the process of designing technological processes.

4. Differential-psychological competence - in the process of developing abilities to design technological processes.

1) A. Zimnyaya defines the concept of "competence" in the following main approaches: 1) "...competencies as a set of contents to be mastered, this is a preselected, structured and didactically organized objective reality (pedagogical interpretation)";

2) "...competencies are intellectual, psychophysiological qualities of the subject, as conditions for successful mastering of the given content; as a result of the expansion of the content of this concept, including knowledge and skills; interpretation of skills as abilities (psychological and practical interpretation)";

3) "... content that has been mastered and is being mastered, but has not yet been updated, that is, mental education, a representation of the content of knowledge, programs for their implementation, methods of actions and algorithms". "Formation of special competence for the future teacher of technological education is the most important" (E.F. Zeer)

"...specific competence implies that the future teacher will develop the ability to design

correctly during his professional career." (AKMarkova);

"... special competence ensures the overall socio-professional quality of a specialist and successful activity of a competitive person" (I.A. Zimnyaya).

The concept of "special competence" can be interpreted as follows:

- "... the ability to solve special problems in a certain professional field and depends on the individual's talent in this field (mathematics, economics, communication, marketing, trade, technology, etc.);

- "... readiness to independently implement the problems of professional and pedagogical activity; ability to solve non-standard pedagogical problems; ability to think professionally; critical evaluation of the results of one's work; acquire new knowledge and skills in the specialty; mastering the skill of designing (sewing items) in teaching students of general secondary education and extracurricular education" - "...readiness to perform professional tasks independently and creatively; ready to objectively evaluate himself and the results of his work"

- "...the ability to solve problems and get the desired results of the work;

- "...the unity of knowledge, skills and competences that ensure professional activity, the tactics of applying one's own skills and motivational ability in practice;

Special competence is the ability to have a sufficiently high level of one's professional activity, to plan one's further professional development. When we theoretically consider the definitions of research issues, the most important elements of special competence include successful professional activity, the ability to solve special problems in a certain professional field, the ability to solve nonstandard pedagogical problems; ability to think professionally; includes a critical assessment of the results of one's work and readiness to perform professional functions independently and creatively.

Summarizing the above, based on a detailed analysis of scientific literature and the above approaches, we come to the conclusion that the concept of "special competence" is multi-valued, multi-variant, and does not have a precise definition. In this regard, based on the analysis of scientific sources and the above concepts (A.A.Kuleshov, E.F.Filippova, V.Ya.Tsvetkov, K.A.Pushkareva and NF Fields) agreed with the opinion of the researchers and made their own opinion about the concept of "special competence" we formed our idea and concept: Special competence is the integrative quality of the future teacher, including the ability to solve non-standard pedagogical problems; ability to think professionally; critical evaluation of the results of one's work; acquire new knowledge and skills in the specialty; mastering the skills of designing (technological processes) in teaching students of general secondary education and extracurricular education" The ability to solve special problems in a certain professional field; as well as readiness to perform professional functions independently and creatively. We agree with the definition of Yu.V.Frolov and A.V.Khutorskoy, according to which the future teacher of technological education (in the design of technological processes) is a perfectly competent specialist . In order to be formed, basic, professional and special competencies must be fully formed.

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